

CLASSROOM LANGUAGE USAGE FOR EFL INSTRUCTORS KNOWING THE “AUDIENCE”

Lola Xayrulloeva, Tashkent,
Uzbekistan World Languages University,
+998909159770
xayrulloeva_lola1995@mail.ru

If we knew what we were doing, it wouldn't be called research, would it? -
ALBERT EINSTEIN

Abstract: This article is devoted to how to use appropriate speech to communicate with learners for conducting classes at auditory. As an instructor, you've determined the nature of your audience and considered where and when you will speak, the next step is to gather information for classroom speech. However, not being in a rush to accumulate data is a crucial way to use them. Also, the research includes bright points of approaching the topic from the audience's perspective, using statistics for impact, quotations, definitions, anecdotes and suitable proverbs while teachers use them within their speech.

Keywords: *Rhetorical clout, blend the quotation, comparison, contrasting, reputable*

Абстракт: Данная статья посвящена использованию соответствующей речи в общении с обучающимися для проведения занятий в аудитории. Как преподаватели, вы определили характер своей аудитории и обдумали, где и когда вы будете выступать. Следующим шагом будет сбор информации для выступления в классе. Однако не спешить с накоплением данных — это решающий способ их использования. Также исследование включает в себя яркие моменты подхода к теме с точки зрения аудитории, использования статистики воздействия, цитат, определений, анекдотов и подходящих пословиц, в то время как учителя используют их в своей речи.

Ключевые слова: *Риторическое воздействие, смешение цитат, сравнение, противопоставление, авторитетность.*

Abstrakt: Ushbu maqola auditoriya darslarini o'tkazishda o'quvchilar bilan muloqot qilish uchun to'g'ri nutqdan qanday foydalanishga bag'ishlangan. O'qituvchi sifatida siz tinglovchilaringizning tabiatini aniqlash va qayerda hamda qachon nutq so'zlashingizni ko'rib chiqish, keyingi qadam esa sinfdagi nutq uchun ma'lumot to'plashdir. Biroq, ma'lumotlarni to'plashga shoshilmaslik ulardan foydalanishning hal qiluvchi usuli hisoblanadi. Shuningdek, tadqiqot mavzuga tinglovchilar nuqtai nazaridan yondashishning yorqin nuqtalarini o'z ichiga oladi, ta'sir qilish uchun statistik ma'lumotlar, iqtiboslar, ta'riflar, latifalar va mos maqollarni o'qituvchilar o'z nutqlarida ishlatadilar.

Kalit so'zlar: *Ritorik ta'sir, iqtibosni aralashtirish, taqqoslash, qarama-qarshilik, obro'li*

Introduction The classroom serves as the principal arena for many learners, particularly those enrolled in foreign language programs, to use and experience the target language, mostly during teacher-led teaching. However, a clear definition of "good language use" is not offered by communicative language training. Teachers typically adopt an eclectic approach, which means that their methods for using language in the classroom will probably differ from one another. This study describes how multi-level multi-section course differ from each other in the amount of teacher/student talk. The data were collected through the book by Joan Detz named "How to write and give a speech" and additional documentation included teacher interviews, final course grades, and end-of-course evaluations. According to practical guide by Joan Detz, our own brain is always the best source of information. "What do I already know about this subject?" ask yourself, after that, write down your ideas. Just jotting down some crude notes at this time; without bothering about order is the best way to speak. Jot down significant details, viewpoints, and concepts—whatever knowledge you already possess. If at all feasible, let your notes sit for a day or two. After that, go over them.

Start looking for particular material now, such as statistics, quotes, definitions, case studies, pop culture allusions, parallels, and contrasts—in other words, specifics that will bolster your main points. It's also crucial to address any issues with insufficient variety in your details. A speech cannot be completed by cramming 38 data in and calling it good. A range of research materials are required, including a few figures, a deft explanation, some excellent examples, a brief summary of the day's events, a first-hand account, and an expert opinion. Having an idea to maintain the audience's interest, you should present a wide range of research. You have the power as the speaker because you get to select the exact subject. It is also up to you to decide what information is retained and what is deleted. It's equally crucial to know what not to say as to what to say. Through speaking during class, just omit: -unimportant specifics -tedious specifics -anything you wouldn't want to be reminded of the following year

-anything you couldn't independently confirm, or anything you wouldn't want to see mentioned in print the next day

VIEW THE TOPIC FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF THE AUDIENCE The only way your audience can comprehend what you're talking about is if they can tie it to their own concepts, issues, and experiences. Thus, consider the topic from their viewpoint rather than your own. Don't simply whine about the issues facing your company, for instance. You may have some valid concerns, but your audience is unlikely to give a damn. Their own issues are already too numerous. Rather, connect your worries to those of them. Identify the "hook" that will catch an audience's interest and assist them grasp your content. Discuss the advantages for the audience. Explain to the audience how their condition would improve if your organization could improve. As an illustration: Let's say you are presenting to raise money for your neighborhood library. How might the public benefit if the library were able to raise additional funds? Would they benefit from Sunday access, extended library hours, a children's reading hour, or a business and career center?

If you tackle the subject from the viewpoint of your audience, your effectiveness will increase. Speaking from a genuine understanding, speakers win the trust and affection of their audiences.

WAYS TO APPLY QUOTATIONS

Next to the originator of a good sentence is the first quoter of it. (Ralph Waldo Emerson)

Quotations are a hit with audiences if you 1. Make use of a quote with persuasive eloquence. Winston Churchill once said, "We have not journeyed all this way across the centuries, across the oceans, across the mountains, across the prairies, because we are made of sugar candy." Jimmy Carter referenced this quote in his acceptance speech as a presidential candidate. 2. Integrate the citation into the narrative. Say nothing like "quote... un-quote." Rather, take a time to let your voice highlight the quote. This succinct but impactful statement was taken from the 2007 Black History Month keynote address written by the Office of Lt. Governor Anthony Brown of Maryland: "Every single one of us... has a responsibility to fulfill and promote the American Dream. In the words of Frederick Douglass, 'Power concedes nothing without a demand. It never did and it never will.'

3. Steer clear of long or intricate quotations. Quotes should be brief. Eliminate or reword any "slow parts."

4. Select a source that makes sense for both the audience and the subject. Walter Hall-stein, the first president of the European Commission, was quoted by Mario Draghi, the president of the European Central Bank, at the Frankfurt [Germany] Chamber of Commerce and Industry in 2013: "... anyone who does not believe in miracles in European matters is not a realist."

5. Look at ease using the quotation. Never quote someone unless you are certain that you can say their name correctly. I once heard someone refer to "the renowned German author, Goethe." Sadly, he mispronounced the name as "Goath," which caused the quotation to lose its impact and the speaker's credibility to crumble.

6. Use quotations sparingly. Don't quote dozens of other people in your speech; instead, let it represent your ideas and area of expertise. You can easily use one or two quotations in a fifteen-minute speech. Recall that as the quantity of your quotations increases, their impact will decrease significantly.

APPLICATION OF EXAMPLES

Giving specific examples will make your point "stick" in the minds of the listeners. Using personal experiences to his advantage, President George W. Bush addressed the nation on stem cell research, saying, "I have friends whose children suffer from juvenile diabetes. I have received a letter from Nancy Reagan regarding President Reagan's battle with Alzheimer's. Leukemia in childhood has been a tragedy for my own family."

APPLICABILITY OF COMPARISONS AND CONTRASTS

Make relatable everyday comparisons that people can understand. Leo Durocher faced jeers when he pulled a pitcher late in a close game while he was the Brooklyn Dodgers manager. A reporter then inquired about his thoughts on the response from the crowd. Duro-cher's analogy? "Church and baseball are alike. Lots of people show up. Few people are aware of this." During his final speech as New York City mayor, Rudolph Giuliani likened the World Trade Center to a massive battlefield. "This is going to be a place that is remembered one hundred and one thousand years from now, like the great battlefields of Europe and of the United States," Giuliani declared while standing next to the rubble at Ground Zero. Valley Forge, Normandy, or Bunker

"Data Protection and Cyber Security" was the topic of a 2012 seminar hosted by the American Chamber of Commerce in Slovakia. Shortly after the event, I happened to notice the publicity while traveling through Bratislava. During his keynote speech, U.S. ambassador H.E. (His Excellency) Theodore Sedgwick emphasized the importance of sharing privacy regulations between the EU and the US. Why? Data can therefore travel across borders with the same ease as people and goods do. In his comparative analysis, Ambassador Sedgwick stated that Slovakia's economy is currently expanding at the fastest rate in Europe.

USAGE OF PROVERBS

In 2013, New York City mayor Michael Bloomberg discussed the need for sensible federal gun control laws, accompanied by families from Newtown, Connecticut, and Vice President Joe Biden. He used the following proverb to highlight his point: The Jewish saying "remembrance is the secret of redemption" goes like this. The lesson is this: We will inevitably repeat the atrocities of the past if we choose to ignore them. However, we can free ourselves from their hold if we keep them in mind and draw lessons from them. That is the reason we are all gathered here today: we feel that it is our duty to assist in ridding our nation of the gun violence that claims lives and shatters hearts on a daily basis, year-round.

APPLICATION OF DEFINITIONS

Definitions are not utilized enough. Too many speakers undervalue the importance of definitions and overuse statistics. That's unfortunate because well-written definitions greatly enhance speeches. Think about these recommendations: a) Explain your terms using common language. Steer clear of "dictionary" definitions. "According to Webster..." sounds weak and unprofessional. b) Consult the Appendix of this book for sources of lively definitions.

•Sir John Quinton (British banker): "Politicians are people who, when they see light at the end of the tunnel, go out and buy some more tunnel."

Jimmy Carter: "The present tax structure is ... just a welfare program for the rich."

c) Give your organization a definition that is unique to you and your terms. Stephen S. Tang, Ph.D., the CEO of the University City Science Center, gave an impressive speech. "As the oldest and largest urban research park in the nation, the Science Center has supported innovation and entrepreneurship in the region since 1963," Dr. Tang said

of Philadelphia's University City Science Center during a 2012 speech in Delaware. She went on to discuss the significance of science centres to a region's vitality. Or, to put it another way, for the past fifty years, we have been creating the future."

USE GUIDE FOR ANECDOTES

Audiences enjoy engaging anecdotes, especially during at classes while long thinking at an academic sphere. What's more, they adore the speakers who share them. Great anecdotes can be found in a number of books and various websites. However, you don't have to spend a lot of time in a library or on the Internet. Your own experiences will provide some of the best research details. Ronald Reagan, dubbed "The Great Communicator," was well aware of the persuasive power of anecdotes. This is a brief autobiographical account that he gave to the National Association of Evangelicals in 1984: I recall attending a war bond rally at Madison Square Garden in New York during World War II. There were notable figures at the rally. After that, (the audience) stayed for a \$54 monthly fee. A few weeks after the United States was attacked on September 11, 2001, Norman Mineta, the former secretary of transportation for the United States, spoke at the University of Rochester, drawing from his own difficult experiences as an American of Japanese descent. After the terrorist attacks, Mineta urged people not to mistreat Arab and Muslim Americans, recalling the horrendous treatment of Japanese Americans during World War II. Mineta's political message was reinforced by his personal story.

APPLYING STATISTICS TO IMPACT

For some people, statistics are uninteresting. These individuals haven't been given the correct statistics. Intriguing statistics can be found if you: Make your audience feel as though the statistics are real. Try saying this: "x number' of teenagers will have babies while they are still children themselves while we sit here for an hour and debate the value of sex education in the schools." Alternatively, "45 people will call our cocaine hot line tonight to ask for assistance while you're watching your favorite TV show." Is it possible that one of the callers is your kid? Simplify the concept of statistics. Saying that your senator would send "X" million items to her constituents this year is insufficient. Explain instead that this equates to roughly three deliveries.

Don't overuse numbers. More than a few numbers at a time can be comprehended by audiences. You risk losing your audience if you use too many statistics. Soroptimist International uses a powerful story and a limited number of statistics to highlight its efforts to improve the lives of women and girls worldwide. The few numbers they do use are carefully selected to have maximum impact and power. Take a look at these figures from a Soroptimist speech from 2013: Seventy-nine percent of those trafficked across international borders are women. Among the 880 million adults without literacy, women make up two thirds. Don't feel bad about using statistics. Sayings like "I hate to bore you with statistics, but..." are common among inexperienced speakers. Following this apology, they continue to engross their audiences with clumsy statistics that are not well chosen or utilized. Steer clear of this pitfalls. If you adhere to the recommendations in

this chapter, you won't have boring statistics. They will, in fact, make your speech much more interesting.

FEW FINAL RESEARCH-RELATED NOTES

A perceptive audience will wonder where you got your information. Verify that each source is reliable and suitable for the audience you are speaking for. Once more, every audience is unique. To satisfy their needs, use a variety of resources. I would like to restate: Make sure your speech contains a variety of material, such as one or two quotes, an example, a few eye-catching statistics, a well-thought-out definition, a comparison, and possibly a mention of the day's news. Your speech will become more engaging, credible, and quote-worthy with this variety. Be advised that some people simply cannot absorb some kinds of information. Personal anecdotes may seem a little silly to "numbers people". "Listeners" might not trust statistics and would rather hear anecdotal evidence instead. "I always try to balance the light with the heavy—a few tears for the human spirit in with the sequins and the fringes," says Bette Midler, describing how she puts together a successful show. Those seeking to gather information for a speech can benefit from the same balance. The variation can be effective and make the speech more memorable.

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